

WAYS OF INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT IN THE SOUTHERN REGIONS OF OUR COUNTRY (IN THE EXAMPLE OF KASHKADARYA AND SURKHANDARYA REGIONS)

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Abstract: In the reforms implemented in our country, great attention is paid to the development of the industrial sector in the structure of the economy. Globalization of the world economy and its transition to new technological development lead to increased competition in international industrial product markets. In order to ensure the competitiveness of local industrial enterprises in the world markets, it is necessary to take a place among the leading countries in the field of science and innovation, to achieve competitiveness in the world market, to find new solutions to the existing problems in the industry, and also to find a solution to the economic security issues arising due to globalization

Keywords: National economy, diversification, modernization, industry, investment activity, innovation, competition, export, competitiveness, industry efficiency.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, special attention has been paid to the development of the industrial sector in our country. In particular, according to the 22nd purpose of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 of January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", it is envisaged to increase the share of industrial products in the GDP by 1.4 times. In addition, this document sets the goals of doubling the production volume of construction materials, textile and electrical engineering products, and 3 times the volume of leather and footwear products. In addition, the tasks of further developing the export potential of local industrial sectors, increasing the volume of finished and semi-finished products in its composition by 3.3 times have been set. In order to achieve these goals, it is necessary to assess the potential for the development of the industrial network in the regions of our country, to identify problems in its development and to develop scientifically based measures for their elimination.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Several aspects of the issues related to the activity of industrial enterprises and the concept of economic stability were studied in the scientific works of foreign economists such as O.M. Kulikova, U.P. Kozlova, N.A. Maksimova, A.S. Gorshkov, I. Ansoff, R. Bellman, B. Ryan. Problems of expanding the range of products produced by industrial enterprises and increasing the competitiveness of these products in the world market, studied by A.U. Burkhanov and other economists. However, the conditions of development of industrial enterprises in the regions and the reasons and shortcomings of the differences between them have not been sufficiently researched. Therefore, it was necessary to carry out large-scale scientific and research work in this direction.

3 DATA AND METHODOLOGY

In the research process of this scientific work, logical thinking, scientific observation, systematic approach, as well as methods of analysis and synthesis were used in the study of statistical data and theories related to the topic. The research used open data statistics of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other state agencies. These data were comparatively analyzed and the issues of industrial policy and its efficiency improvement were analyzed. In addition, relevant conclusions were formed based on the analysis of important aspects of theoretical literature and empirical research on the topic of industrial policy and its main directions.

4 ANALYSIS AND RESULTS.

In addition, the growth dynamics of industrial production in these regions is not stable. The volume of growth rates varies significantly by year, for example, the highest growth of industrial production in Kashkadarya was recorded in 2021 (115.4%), and in Surkhandarya in 2018 (128.1%). At the same time, the volume of industrial production in Kashkadarya region decreased significantly in 2010, 2012 and 2019, and in Surkhandarya region in 2018.

However, it should be noted that the change in the volume of production of industrial products in the regions differs by region. For example, in 2017, the volume of industrial production in the Surkhandarya region decreased by 16.8%, but the volume of industrial production increased in six of the 14 districts and cities of the region (Termiz, Termiz, Altinsoy, Zharqurgan, Sherobod and Sariosiyo districts). We can observe a similar trend in the case of Kashkadarya region. In 2019, the volume of industrial production in Kashkadarya region decreased by 6.3% compared to 2018, while industrial production increased in nine out of 14 districts and cities in the region. The volume of industrial production in the region has significantly decreased in Kasbi, Qamashi, Mubarak and Koson districts. These data indicate that the industrial production potential in the regions is not fully used,

there are problems in the field of diversification of production in the regions, and the current industrial development policy does not take into account the specific characteristics of the regions.

The analysis of the development of the industrial network in the southern region in terms of districts and cities shows that there are significant differences in the level of industrial development in the districts of the region.

For example, in 2021, industrial products in Kashkadarya region were mainly produced in 3 districts, Nishan, Gozor districts and the city of Karshi, these areas accounted for 59.6% of the industrial production of the region.

During 2010-2021, we can see that the share of Mubarak district in the production volume of industrial products of the region decreased from 51.2 percent to 3.3 percent.

On the one hand, this situation is explained by the increase in the production of industrial products in some districts of the region. During this period, it increased 88.1 times in Nishan district, 25.2 times in Dehkanabad district, 22.9 times in Kasbi district and 20.4 times in Yakkabog district. On the other hand, it is explained by the fact that during this period, the volume of industrial production in Mubarak district decreased by five times.

The analysis of industrial production in the Surkhandarya region by districts also shows that there are significant differences in this indicator between districts. In 2021, 61.8% of industrial products were produced in five regions of the region (Termiz, Zharkurgan, Sariosia, Shorchi and Sherobod districts).

During this period, the share of industrial products in the production of industrial products increased significantly in the city of Termiz and Sariosia districts, while in the districts of Denov, Zhargorgon and Shorchi, on the contrary, its share decreased significantly (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: The share of districts in the industrial production of Surkhandarya region in 2010 and 2021 (in percentage of the total)

In 2010, these districts accounted for 41.1% of regional industrial production, and in 2021, their share was 30.5%.

At the same time, unlike the Kashkadarya region, the reduction of the share of the region's industrial products production was not due to a decrease in the production volume of industrial products, but as a result

of the lower growth rates of the production volume compared to other districts. In particular, during this period, the production of industrial products in the region increased by 8.8 times, while in Denov, Zhargorgon and Shorchi districts it increased by 4.5, 7.4 and 7.5 times, respectively.

The data presented above show that there are significant differences in the volume of industrial production in the regions of the southern region. On the one hand, this is the result of differences in the specialization of these regions, and on the other hand, it indicates that the potential of the regions has not been fully realized.

In our study, the structure of industrial production in the southern region was also analyzed.

In Kashkadarya region, during 2010-2021, the production volume of the mining industry decreased by 40%, and its share in the regional industrial production volume decreased from 70.7% to 11.1%. On the other hand, the production of electricity increased by 25.5 times and its share in industrial products of the region reached from 3.5% to 23.4%. Positive results were also achieved in the development of the production industry in the region, these industries grew 9.7 times and their share in industrial products reached 84.6% from 25.5%. The textile, chemical and food industries are the leaders in the manufacturing industries. These industrial enterprises account for 45.2% of the products created by the manufacturing industry in the region. In recent years, the chemical industry in the region has developed rapidly, in 2010-2021, the production volume of this industry has increased 25.3 times, and the share of production industries in products has reached 30.6% from 3.4%. The main part of the products created in the textile industry is kalava yarn.

In the Surkhandarya region, unlike Kashkadarya region, the share of manufacturing industries in the composition of industrial products is higher, and during the research period, the production in these industries increased by 8.9 times and their share in the region reached 89.4%. In turn, the share of electricity production enterprises in the production of industrial products decreased from 7.5 percent to 5.4 percent. The share of the mining industry in the production of industrial products in the region is 3.7 percent. The number of enterprises engaged in the extraction of existing underground resources in the region has increased, and the volume of their products has increased 6.4 times. However, at the same time, taking into account the presence of large reserves of underground resources in the region, we can conclude that the development potential of these industries is not fully utilized.

Textiles and food industries play an important role in the processing industries. 64.5% of products produced in processing industries in the region are created in industrial enterprises of this sector. Also, production of other non-metallic mineral products, production of oil and coke processing products, and

production of clothing products have a significant contribution to the composition of industrial products.

Wine, vodka and beer accounted for 1.9% of food production (3.4% in January-December 2020). The highest share of production of consumer products by region was 19.5% in the city of Termiz, 14.0% in Shorchi district, and 12.9% in Denov district. Also, in terms of the growth rate of the production of consumer products, higher than the regional growth rate (110.1%) were Bandikhon (183.9%), Oltinsoy (136.0%), Sariosiyo (134.1%), Uzun (128.3%), Shorchi (125.1%), Muzrabot (125.0%), Jarqorgan (123.2%) and Angor (121.2%) was recorded in the districts

In 2021, small businesses in Kashkadarya region will spend 4922.7 billion. Soum industrial products were produced, and its share in the total volume of production was 26.3%. In terms of regions, the highest share of small business in the production of industrial products is in Kitab district (98.7% share in total industrial production), Shahrisabz (84.0%), Yakkabog (80.7%), Shiraqi (79.5%), districts and the city of Shahrisabz (77.6%).

The implementation of the localization program for the production of finished products, components and materials also had an impact on achieving high growth rates of industrial production in the region. 1144.8 billion for 80 projects included in this program. products worth soums were produced. 6.6 mln. of products produced within the framework of the localization program. Exported in the amount of US dollars.

Export diversification means increasing the volume of exported goods and achieving a balanced composition of exports. Below, we will show the changes in the volume of exports over the years in the example of Kashkadarya and Surkhondarya regions. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: The volume of exports by region until March 2010-2023 (as a percentage of the total volume)

Of course, increasing export has a significant impact not only on the development of local entrepreneurship, but also on the economy of this region.

Sherabad (18.8%), Termiz (14.1%), Denov (11.6%), Zhargorgon (10.8%) districts are the regions with the

highest share in the export structure of Surkhondarya region. Altinsoy (2.8%), Shorchi (2.8%), Bandikhon (1.2%), Kyziriq (1.1%) districts are considered the lowest regions.

In the Kashkadarya region, the regions with the highest share in exports are Karshi (27.3%), Koson (13.9%), Kasbi (13.4%), Yakkabog (6.5%), Guzor (6.4%). districts. Shahrisabz city (0.8%), Mubarak (1.7%), Dehkanabad (2.1%), Chirakchi (2.7%), Nishon (3.1%) districts are the lowest regions.

Also, the share of the high-tech sector in the manufacturing industry in the region does not even reach 1% (Surkhondarya - 0.3%, Kashkadarya - 0.5%) and is relatively lower than this indicator for our country (Fig. 3.2.3). The main part of industrial enterprises in the region is low-tech industrial enterprises. The share of these enterprises in the production of industrial products is 65 percent in Surkhondarya region, and 47.2 percent in Kashkadarya region.

As can be seen from these data, the majority of industrial products in Surkhondarya region are developed by low- and medium-low-tech enterprises, the share of medium-high-tech enterprises in Kashkadarya region is 22, in line with the average indicator for our country. is 3 percent. However, more than 50 percent of industrial products are created by low- and medium-low technology enterprises.

Figure 3 Composition of industrial environments by technological level

It is necessary to ensure the achievement of development results by using development means (resources, sources and conditions of development, forms of influence) based on the regional industrial policy.

In our opinion, the logical-structural model of regional industry development policy should cover the following:

1. The goals of development, i.e., the goals of industrial development of the region should be determined, ensuring the growth of GDP, increasing competitiveness, increasing the production of products with high added value, increasing the production of products with high scientific capacity. breeding and hakoza.

2. Identify development tools. That is, attracting the necessary resources to achieve this goal, choosing the levers of state policy,

3. Development results. These results are a system of performance indicators that should be achieved, and are important for assessing the effectiveness of industrial policy and solving existing problems.

Clearly defining the outcomes of regional industrial policy is essential for assessing the effectiveness of industrial policy. In this case, industrial policy implies economic results as well as social and environmental results. In addition, along with the final results, intermediate results should be determined. Intermediate results allow to determine whether the industrial policy is in line with the implementation deadlines.

CONCLUSION

In the southern region of our country, industrial production has grown significantly, many new types of industrial products have been launched. At the same time, we can see that there are certain problems in the development of industrial enterprises in the region.

1. The instability of the growth of industrial production in the region. In the research period, the presence of significant fluctuations in the growth of industrial production over the years indicates the high impact of changes in the internal and especially foreign market conditions on the regional industry.

2. The share of industry in the formation of the GNP of the region is not high, agriculture occupies an important place in the formation of the gross regional product of the region. In Surkhandarya region, the share of industry has slightly increased, while in Kashkadarya region, on the contrary, the contribution of industry in the formation of the gross regional product has decreased significantly. This, in turn, indicates that the industrial development potential in the region is not being used effectively.

3. The analysis of the composition of industrial products by technological level shows that the main part of industrial products in the region consists of low and medium-low technological products. That is, the number of industrial enterprises producing products with high added value is small. This limits the possibility of increasing the weight of industrial products in the formation of GNI and increasing the importance of the industry in creating additional jobs.

It is important to implement an industrial policy that takes into account the specific characteristics of the region, from the development of the industrial network in the region, turning it into the driving sectors of the regional economy.

Industrial policy is effective only if it is implemented in harmony with many other economic policies, including structural policy, investment policy, foreign trade policy, fiscal policy and other economic policies. Therefore, it is necessary to develop and implement complex measures consisting of all macro-economic policy levers to ensure the industrial production of the region.

In our opinion, in order to increase the importance of the industrial network in ensuring the economic stability of the region, it is appropriate for the regional industrial policy to cover the following areas:

Diversification of industry production plays an important role in ensuring the stability of industrial production in the region. The process of diversification should take into account changes in the regional industrial composition of the foreign market. At the same time, it is necessary to pay attention to creating conditions for the production of high added value and technologically complex types of industrial products.

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